

The Effects of Children's Games on the Psychology and Development of 0-6 Age Group Children

To cite this article: Collaborate, Current Science, Volume 5, No. 5-9, 2023, p. 43 – 70. - 0099-0001-2309-02103.

Our studies are in a format accredited, approved, and supported by EAALS - European Academic Studies and Laboratory Services. (“Scientific Studies - Current Science Georgia”) “EAALS offers all our works, services, and publications to the world scientists at the stage of carrying our control, accreditation, and support processes to the international platform.” (“CURRENT SCIENCE”) (“Scientific Studies - Current Science Georgia”)

ISSN: 2667-9515

Barcode: 977266795001

Editors Group:

Concessionaire: Tsisana Kharabadze

Niyaz Bokvadze

1

**THIS JOURNAL INCLUDED IN MANY INDEXES, INCLUDING
ADVANCED SCIENCES INDEX. ADVANCED SCIENCES INDEX (ASI)
EUROPEAN SCIENCE EVALUATION CENTER KIRCHSTRASSE 4.56761 |
RHINELAND-PALATINATE, GERMANY PHONE: +49(177) 8684-353
PHONE: +49(177) 8684-353 EMAILS:**

ASI@EUROPE.DE

CURRENT SCIENCE

Prof. Sabrina Corbi

Prof. Samantha Lewes

Assoc. Prof. Osman Doruk

""• Current Science Multidisciplinary Academic Journal with Review Panel is a monthly multidisciplinary academic" ("CURRENT SCIENCE A Different Look at Traffic Sociology and Driver ...") ("Scientific Studies - Current Science Georgia") ("Scientific Studies - Current Science Georgia") Science Georgia") journal with a multi-science peer-review." ("Scientific Studies - Current Science Georgia") ("Scientific Studies - Current Science Georgia")

""The magazine will be at the subscriber's address in the first week of the month."" ("Scientific Studies - Current Science Georgia")

• The journal continues to be included in all international rankings and registrations. Quality articles and publications accelerate this ("Scientific Studies - Current Science Georgia")

CURRENT SCIENCE

""• Response or rejection time for applications varies between 30 and 90 days.""
("Scientific Studies - Current Science Georgia")

Author(s) Name Surname:

İlknur GENÇOĞLU YILDIRIM

University:

Northwest University

Department: Psychology

Title: Doctor

Date: 13 .08

Abstract

The game has significant importance in several aspects of life. Like the significance of nutrition, sleep, and health for a child, play also holds equal importance. In order to effectively contribute to a child's cognitive development, social-emotional development, self-care skills, language development, psycho-motor skills, and overall development, the type of game engaged in should remain consistent. While engaging in play is mostly an internal process, it is important to establish a clear correlation between the resources provided to a kid and their own desires and requirements. This is why play is an activity that lacks certain constraints or predetermined outcomes.

Constraint

The limitations of the research are limited to the scope of the subject in the light of world literature and data. The research was limited to closely related author and literature topics. Restricted by literature review.

Notifications

Evaluation: Evaluated by internal and external consultants.

Conflict of Interest: The authors declared no conflict of interest regarding this article.

Financial Disclosure: The authors reported no use of financial support for this article.

Ethical Statement

Publication ethics of the relevant regulations of our university; It is a national-based scientific study that aims to ensure that scientific research and publications are carried out in accordance with basic principles such as honesty, openness, objectivity, and respect for the findings and creations of others, and works for the realization of these principles in the field of related sciences.

Abstract

The game has significant importance in several aspects of life. Like the significance of nutrition, sleep, and health for a child, play also holds equal importance. In order to promote children's cognitive development, social-emotional development, self-care skills, language development, psycho-motor skills, and overall development, it is crucial that the type of play engaged in remains consistent. While the act of play is mostly driven by internal factors, it is important to establish a clear correlation between the resources provided to a kid and their desires and requirements. This is why play is an activity that lacks specific goals or predetermined outcomes. This activity is subject to modification based on the duration of time spent with the youngster. While often seen as a form of amusement and leisure, engaging in games may provide novel insights and feelings, particularly when shared with a kid. Moreover, this activity has the potential to foster a positive learning environment conducive to the acquisition of

CURRENT SCIENCE

values-based education. This research focused on investigating the impact of Values Education on children in the 0-6 age group.

Keywords: *Child Development, Play in Child Development. Children's Games, Games, Games and Values Education, Preschool Game*

Introduction

The game is designed to provide youngsters with an enjoyable experience. It is a source of satisfaction to engage in an activity with the intention of generating something. One innate characteristic is activity. For instance, when a youngster imitates someone's conduct during a game, it indicates that they are influenced by that individual's actions. The subject of discussion pertains to the concept of games. The individual in question exhibits a preference for purchasing items only for the sake of personal enjoyment. In addition to becoming a trainer, there is another activity. The involvement of children in gaming activities has been shown to have a good impact on their cognitive development and mental processes, hence influencing crucial aspects of their overall well-being. Additionally, it imparts valuable skills. Children engage in games that allow them to explore and develop their own strengths. As individuals acquire new vocabulary, their capacity for creative thinking expands. The acquisition of problem-solving abilities is enhanced. Children acquire new ideas and values via play at the same time. Furthermore, individuals acquire knowledge via schooling and afterwards begin to implement it.

Values education plays a crucial role in fostering the development of children into adults who possess a well-rounded personality and exhibit a harmonious moral compass. The family plays a crucial role in imparting values education to the kid initially. The environment and the educational institution are after the family unit. The impact of the environment on both the kid and their surroundings is evident, as the educational experiences acquired at school serve as a manifestation of this effect. Hence, both the environment and the educational institution have significant influence. Given the current era of technological advancements, it is evident that media and social media platforms have become more prevalent. This observation highlights the significant responsibility associated with imparting societal ideals to the younger generation. Hence, it is crucial to analyze, interpret, and assess the materials developed based on educational and training curricula, as well as school programs, with regards to values education and the methodologies used for children.

During the early childhood phase, namely during the age range of 0-6 years, a significant developmental milestone known as the emergence of personality takes place. It is crucial for children to have an appropriate attitude towards others who possess diverse features and come from various cultural backgrounds. This approach posits that the cultivation of tolerance is essential for fostering a

CURRENT SCIENCE

harmonious community, hence underscoring the need of nurturing people who are well-adjusted and in good health. The cultivation of tolerance and empathy in children has the potential to enhance the overall well-being of civilizations. Therefore, it is of utmost significance to cultivate the virtue of tolerance from the preschool years. Additionally, the acquisition of empathy has a crucial position in relation to fostering harmony within the prevailing social structure. It is essential to establish provisions within the realm of education to ensure the integration of values education. This entails the meticulous preparation of educational programs and the incorporation of values education into the curriculum. The incorporation of values education into educational and training programs facilitates a deeper comprehension among youngsters, hence fostering the development of well-adjusted individuals who possess a harmonious relationship with both them and their surroundings. The degree of welfare and moral self-actualization people experience in society is favorably influenced by the extent to which they demonstrate consistency, empathy, and overall health in their moral lives.

Social and moral values have a significant position within the realm of human existence. Values may be described as moral and ethical frameworks that are widely recognized and regarded as significant within educated society. The subject matter pertains to the examination of correct and incorrect cognitive processes within the domain of values-based education.

In order to cultivate individuals with optimal mental and physical well-being, it is essential to prioritize education and training from the early childhood years, namely during the kindergarten phase. Individuals need the capacity to openly manifest their imaginative faculties, emotions, and ideas, in order to cultivate self-regulation, exhibit empathy towards the rights of others, and uphold their own cultural principles. These youngsters have the potential to establish contemporary and democratic societies.

The youngsters who have just complete the values education course have acquired the knowledge and skills necessary to begin their lives on an equitable basis. Individuals possess a remarkable capacity to readily adjust to various circumstances throughout their extensive educational journey. Given the contemporary era characterized by technological advancements, individuals are actively engaged in the use of computers. They exhibit higher levels of efficacy in interpersonal communication within the familial context as well as in intergenerational communication among offspring. They demonstrate a high degree of adaptability in the context of educational environments.

Methodology

The notion of value is often used interchangeably with the notions of our way of life and our current way of life. Value may be conceptualized as an abstract construct that represents the

CURRENT SCIENCE

worth or significance attributed to anything. In this context, value encompasses symbols, ideologies, ideas, and experiences as a collective entity. The presence of values may be influenced by several factors, including familial relationships, social connections, educational institutions, and religious beliefs. Values do not emerge in isolation. The formation of societies characterized by tangible and favorable values is contingent upon the enduring commitment of people who uphold such values.

Values education is acquired via the process of socialization experienced by people. Values education is not bound by limitations of time and location. When should values education be provided? The inquiry has a singular response, which always necessitates its provision. Nevertheless, the incorporation of values education at the pre-school phase has significant significance in the formation of people' character. The kid has the capacity to acquire and provide values education in many settings, including inside the home and at school.

Values empower individuals to exert control over their conduct. The person is introduced into a preexisting and established environment, and as the individual develops, they conform to the environmental factors and undergo cultural adaptation. If he fails to adjust, he will experience dissatisfaction.

The cultivation of love and respect towards individuals is of utmost significance in fostering social cohesion and peace. This pertains to the recognition and reverence given to others based on their inherent sacredness, ability to deal with challenges, perceived superiority, mere existence, age, and personal values. Establishing a relationship and fostering communication based on mutual respect is associated with enhanced well-being and increased longevity.

It is essential for parents and educators to exhibit reverence towards the physical and emotional attributes, inclinations, and cognitive processes of children starting from their early formative years. Furthermore, they must adhere to the guidelines they establish for their children.

In order to instill the value of respect in a kid, it is imperative to consistently demonstrate courteous and considerate treatment towards them. Children who get respectful treatment tend to exhibit similar behavior towards others and adhere to ethical principles. Etiquette in daily life is instructing children on the principles and behaviors necessary for treating others with respect and courtesy. The need for research on values education is steadily growing, with a rising interest and desire among individuals. Educational psychologists and social psychologists

CURRENT SCIENCE

conduct distinct research endeavors aimed at enhancing the achievement of children in society and fostering their adherence to ethical principles and moral values.

The whole of emotional experiences engenders feelings of proximity, fascination, and connection towards the kid or an object. In the realm of values education, the first stage of acquiring knowledge pertaining to the value of love centers on the fundamental role played by family and parents.

The development of children in a nurturing familial setting may foster the establishment of interpersonal connections and effective communication skills, which extend beyond human interactions to include relationships with other living entities. The child's demonstration of conscientiousness in carrying out a task reflects a feeling of personal responsibility stemming from their efforts. It is essential to provide children the chance to assume and fulfill duties assigned to them at a young age. Considering this matter, it is important to do this action in order to cultivate youngsters into humans capable of successfully executing assigned responsibilities in the future.

The timely provision of responsibility education may foster the development of a mature individual who adheres to societal norms and ethical principles, exhibits patriotism and compassion towards fellow citizens, demonstrates environmental consciousness, and displays respect towards others in their immediate surroundings.

Collaborative work refers to the collective efforts of individuals who join forces either in unison or independently, with the aim of achieving a common objective. Collaboration refers to an individual's inclination to actively engage with others in pursuit of shared objectives and commitments, so combining their expertise, abilities, and endeavors. The acquisition of this talent is seen as an essential component of highly cohesive civilizations.

The formation and evolution of democracy have significant importance within the societal context. The acquisition of cooperative behavior in children often begins during the kindergarten age. However, it is worth noting that group work conducted within pre-school education platforms significantly contributes to the active development of this behavior. The acquisition of the concept of collaboration in children mostly occurs via engagement in play activities. The youngster, upon achieving a specific objective or attaining success via collaboration with others in their environment, comprehends the significance and indispensability of the value they have acquired. Therefore, it is essential that families and the

CURRENT SCIENCE

familial context, as well as kindergarten education and the surrounding environment, provide children with many chances and tasks that foster cooperation with their peers.

The trajectory of play serves as a conduit for the child's acquisition of knowledge and development of interpersonal skills. During the developmental stage often seen between the ages of 2 and 3, children engage in social play by forming a circle and selecting companions with whom they choose to participate in various games. Additionally, they engage in communication with their peers while actively engaged in play. Self-control refers to an individual's capacity to regulate their own actions and responses in alignment with their desired objectives, hence facilitating the attainment of these objectives. Individual autonomy refers to an individual's capacity to voluntarily adhere to established laws and regulations without succumbing to other forces. It encompasses the ability to exercise self-control, limit urges and wants, and effectively regulate one's emotions and ideas within the realm of self.

Kindergarten-aged children have limited proficiency in topics that need cognitive self-regulation processes, such as redirecting failed efforts towards other approaches, managing outcomes, and consistently evaluating progress towards a desired objective. Parents can instill the desired values in their children via a limited number of behavioral interventions that may be implemented inside the home environment.

Honesty refers to the act of expressing information without distortion or deception. The concept entails refraining from engaging in deceptive actions towards others as a result of one's own conduct. Furthermore, it is essential to optimize resource use via the adoption of an impartial methodology when making critical judgments. The acquisition of the virtue of honesty has significance in relation to the fulfillment of parental commitments to their offspring and the cultivation of a foundation of trust within the kid.

Children acquire moral and ethical principles via the observation and interpretation of their parents' conduct towards them. The failure of parents to uphold their commitments to their children and their omission of truth-telling contribute to the emergence of mistrust inside the kid, prompting them to resort to falsehoods when faced with challenging circumstances. The observation that parents exhibit excessive reactivity in response to their children's errors or administer punitive measures serves as an impediment to the child's acquisition of this value.

The concept of injustice encompasses many forms of suffering and include efforts to combat poverty, among other issues. The individual has the challenge of patiently enduring the

CURRENT SCIENCE

lingering impact of distressing circumstances and occurrences, refraining from expressing discontent, and persevering through the aftermath. Patience may be seen to achieve spiritual and mental outcomes, which are experienced via many facets of human existence, including emotions, thoughts, and behaviors. It involves deliberately enduring, resisting, and persevering, while awaiting the desired outcome, even in the presence of challenges, dangers, and setbacks. Within the context of this established trajectory, the virtue of patience assumes a crucial role in fostering equilibrium and concord. It serves as a vital force that empowers individuals in their endeavors and confrontations throughout life. By imbuing existence with purpose, patience ultimately paves the way for success and facilitates the attainment of happiness.

The manifestation of a significant value can be discerned through the actions and cognitive processes of virtuous and knowledgeable individuals who willingly and unreservedly share their resources with others, while simultaneously preventing any hindrance to the assistance required by those in need. Moreover, these individuals exhibit the fortitude to proactively assume responsibility and consider it their moral obligation to provide aid.

He acknowledges and embraces the assistance that is offered to him in relation to the pedagogical attributes that are evident throughout the implementation of values education in youngsters. The youngster has an increased sensitivity to his surroundings. Children provide accounts of instances in which individuals want assistance. Children possess the ability to perceive those in their immediate environment who need assistance. Children possess the ability to aid and support to anyone in their immediate vicinity. Children demonstrate their willingness to assist via both verbal communication and nonverbal cues. When a youngster needs assistance, they seek support from their immediate environment. Expressing gratitude towards a youngster for their assistance is a common behavioral practice. In adverse circumstances, the youngster consistently exhibits veracity.

The youngster is required to articulate the potential ramifications that may ensue in situations when he fails to exhibit honesty. The youngster acknowledges and assumes the repercussions of failing to exhibit honesty. The youngster exercises emotional regulation. The youngster demonstrates compliance with established regulations in the absence of adult supervision.

The objective of providing values education to children is to cultivate people who possess strong character, moral principles, and distinct personalities, so enabling them to effectively

CURRENT SCIENCE

integrate into society. Various factors, including family, school, environment, media, and social media, significantly contribute to the facilitation of values education, which entails the transmission of values to young individuals.

Educational institutions have a significant duty in imparting societal ideals to the younger generation. Therefore, it is crucial to analyze the textbooks designed for children's classes in terms of values education within the context of the curriculum and educational program. This analysis plays a significant role in uncovering the prevailing values.

The youngster has a strong sense of determination in completing a given activity. The youngster defers his wishes when deemed appropriate. The youngster articulates instances that elicit both exhilaration and apprehension for him. The youngster exhibits composure under stressful situations. The youngster demonstrates adaptive behavior when exposed to unfamiliar situations. The youngster exhibits behaviors indicative of refraining from causing physical damage to others.

Opinions and Theories on the Game

Educators, instructors, philosophers, and psychologists have advocated for the game as a primary educational instrument and essential aspect of a child's development. They have underscored the inherent usefulness of games and have presented many perspectives and ideas on the subject. The perspectives of educators, instructors, and philosophers towards the game, spanning from historical times to the present day, may be summarized as follows:

Michel de Montaigne (1533-1592) posited the notion that the physical body of human beings need to be cultivated, while contending that the soul cannot be subjected to training. Furthermore, Montaigne advocated for a comprehensive assessment of an individual's education, considering all aspects of their development.

The individual expressed opposition towards excessive emphasis on cognitive education and proposed that acquired knowledge should not solely be taught and practiced, but also applied, transferred to real-life contexts, and evaluated. Additionally, the individual regarded play as a valuable learning environment for children, challenging the long-held belief among adults that play was merely a means of entertainment and distraction, and considered it as a meaningful and purposeful activity.

CURRENT SCIENCE

Friedrich Frobel (1782-1852) directed his attention on the concept of play, serving as an intermediary between two distinct and divergent subjects, namely the natural-spiritual realm and intellect. Frobel claimed that the game ought to be regarded as the preeminent spiritual pursuit for individuals, since it has a uniting influence and functions like to a mechanism.

The incorporation of the game into kindergarten teaching was widely recognized as a significant development, largely attributed to the contributions of Frobel. According to the individual's perspective, play is considered a crucial need for personal development. Moreover, it is posited that play has a comparable level of significance in the lives of children as work does in the lives of adults.

The acquisition of knowledge and skills may be facilitated in children via the use of play-based educational approaches. The acquisition of information in the game is enduring. The author suggested that educational and learning toys facilitate the development of essential skills necessary for navigating life, since they promote independent learning.

According to Frobel, play is the fundamental element that shapes an individual's current life and is the most genuine and emotionally fulfilling activity within the context of kindergarten.

According to Maria Montessori (1870-1952), the activities, values, exercises, games, experiences, and studies of a child are classified as labor rather than play. This phenomenon occurs when a person turns to a certain course of action when they are unable to locate a more advantageous alternative within the context of their life's circumstances. The youngster enters a developmental stage when he engages in educational activities while simultaneously seeking self-improvement via recreational games. Montessori referred to this developmental phase as the period of sensitivity throughout the first six years of a child's life. She emphasized the need of nurturing this phase via play and ensuring thorough assessment.

The Relationship between the Games Learned by the Child and Values Education

Socialization is an ongoing and comprehensive process that covers the development of behavioral patterns in relation to one's surroundings and interactions with other individuals. The game facilitates the acquisition of communication skills, social etiquette, and an understanding of societal norms among individuals.

CURRENT SCIENCE

Acquire knowledge on the term "we" in lieu of "me". The concept of "game" has significant value in a child's social development and linguistic abilities, ranking as the second most important emotional nutrient behind love.

During the process of engaging in games, children are exposed to a wide range of emotions and acquire the ability to regulate and manage these emotional experiences. During the process of play, children can both experience and develop their ability to express emotions. Children get novel experiences. Children engage in the act of defending their beliefs, get enjoyment from various activities, experience feelings of anger, and encounter moments of surprise. Children are responsible for doing all these tasks.

The inclusion of play-based activities has significant value in the field of children's pedagogy. Assisting the youngster in identifying their fundamental interests, wants, inclinations, and emotional challenges might be beneficial.

Children can manifest their emotions of anger, aggression, and frustration, which they may struggle to articulate well, via their engagement in play activities. The individual can demonstrate the emotional state of affection and the manifestation of joy once again by means of engaging in playful activities. Through this method, he inadvertently reveals his own thoughts and emotions to his parents.

According to Freud (1920), he was the first to observe that children express their emotions via their play activities. He observed the correlation between fantasy activities and play and posited that youngsters undergo unconscious wants and challenges throughout their engagement in games.

Like how adults engage in conversations and introspection over the challenges they face in their life, they persistently engage in this iterative process until reaching a resolution. Play serves as an initial foundation for a youngster. The individuals in question endeavor to get insight into their emotions by re-experiencing them within the context of their games. According to Özdoğan (2000:115), there are several options available for the growth of children, including education, enhancement of cognitive abilities, and the acquisition of new behaviors. One crucial aspect of child development that warrants attention is the social development. According to Saracho (1998), play plays a significant role in fostering social development and education in individuals. The game facilitates the development and disclosure of people' social behavior.

CURRENT SCIENCE

Through engaging in interactive experiences with others during gameplay, children acquire valuable social skills. These skills include the capacity to collaborate effectively, comprehend the principles of collaboration and sharing, and develop problem-solving abilities as they navigate challenges encountered within the context of play.

The difference between those who exhibit loyalty to their respective profession and those who demonstrate independence from their area lies in their distinct social accomplishments, experiences, and personal qualities.

When examining the distinctions in socialization between individuals who are loyal versus independent, research has indicated that loyal individuals are more influenced by external cognitive resources and cues from others compared to those who are independent in their respective domains. Consequently, loyal individuals exhibit higher levels of sociability and are more susceptible to the effects of sociability.

Consequently, the significance of play in the domains of social-emotional development and cognitive development is substantial. The many roles that the individual assumes inside the game facilitate his ability to develop empathy towards others, get insights into his own sexual identity, and foster effective communication with his peers. Through the process of engaging with the external environment within the context of his gaming experiences, the individual acquires the ability to decipher and comprehend various occurrences and strategic plans as if he were reliving them. This enables him to effectively internalize the rules, assume leadership roles or function as a member of a team inside the game, and experience both victory and defeat.

From The Literature

Play in the preschool period plays a significant role in the development of a child's values education. It is an entertainment activity that involves the use of metaphorical thought, language, movement, or objects for the purpose of enjoyment. The playful interaction between the child and their play partner, as indicated by their smile or laughter, is a determining factor in this process.

Children between the ages of one and three prefer games that include elements of movement, music, and repetition. Children engage in a variety of physical activities such as stacking, knocking over, rolling, picking up, and dispersing things. They also participate in activities

CURRENT SCIENCE

involving movement, such as hopping, leaping, sprinting, hiding, and catching. Additionally, children have a fondness for games that include sound and motion imitation.

During that period, children engage in repetitive play, repeatedly engaging in the same game. The purpose of this action is to comprehensively document the motion, auditory elements, and contextual circumstances inside one's memory. Starting at the age of three, children develop a fondness for ring games and mini competitions, engaging in regular social interactions. Experiencing success in games that rely on attentiveness and adherence to rules may be an enjoyable endeavor.

During early childhood, namely between the ages of 5 and 6, children's game choices start to exhibit gender-based differences. Those often emulate their parents or those within their own social networks, so becoming personal role models. Within the context of their theatrical works, the playwrights assume the roles that are most appropriate for their respective characters' conditions and behaviors.

During the developmental stage spanning from 7 to 11 years old, the impact of formal education becomes readily apparent. Currently, there is a proliferation of novel attributes, including group affiliation, advocacy, competitive dynamics, peer influence, and reciprocal influence. Consequently, individuals exhibit a strong affinity towards sports and arts-oriented performances, groups, and contests (Azaklı, 2010).

Adolescents within the age range of 11 to 15 years (perhaps somewhat earlier for females) have begun the stage of pubertal development. Peer solidarity is a prevalent phenomenon in which individuals have a feeling of belonging and camaraderie inside a group. This fosters the development of team spirit and an increase in competitive tendencies. Moreover, this social dynamic allows for the potential to influence and be affected by others, even those of the opposing sex. Individuals have a strong affinity for competitive events and contests, particularly those centered around sports and artistic endeavors, as seen by their enthusiasm for exhibitions and organizations in these domains.

Children's games exhibit many characteristics based on their content structures, age appropriateness, social phenomena, and socio-economic circumstances. Researchers have classified games based on these characteristics. The categorization of games offers significant use in the context of academic research investigations.

CURRENT SCIENCE

Piaget (1962) and Smilansky (1968) conducted research to identify the preferred game categories based on cognitive domains, whereas Parten (1932) examined game preferences based on social factors. Piaget (1962) categorized games based on cognitive developmental domains.

The use of workout games, symbolic game exercises, and game exercises with established regulations is observed.

Piaget proposed a sequential framework consisting of three phases to elucidate the progression of game development over the first seven years of an individual's existence. These stages are delineated as practice game work, symbolic play work, and rule play work. These regions are referred regarded as the corresponding domains of sensory-motor, preoperational, and concrete operational intelligences.

The subsequent stage involves the integration of movement and manipulation, first occurring by accident and afterwards progressing towards deliberate actions. At this point, the kid begins to establish objectives and actively endeavors to convert playful activities into structured tasks.

Symbolic play, within the context of labor, may manifest when practice games acquire symbolic qualities. This occurs when an individual's building work or action sequences take on symbolic representations.

Playwork, when engaged in collectively, has the potential to transform into 'games with rules' where the rules themselves may emerge as victorious.

Rationale of the Study

The family, serving as a significant social and emotional milieu, has paramount importance for children. The family plays a crucial role in facilitating the child's assimilation into various societal strata and in instilling values, both via direct and indirect means. Throughout history and in several epochs, there has been a consistent pursuit of certain personality qualities in individuals, namely honesty, love, respect, compassion, and justice.

The presence of appropriate role models within the home setting plays a crucial role in fostering the well-rounded development of children across social, emotional, and moral domains. In Maslow's hierarchy of requirements, it is posited that after a child's fundamental physiological

CURRENT SCIENCE

needs are satisfied, they need emotional support, affection, guidance, and autonomy in order to progress in their developmental journey. Families exhibiting diverse socio-cultural features manifest distinct sets of values and attitudes.

Results

Self-awareness, which pertains to a child's ability to comprehend and assess their own ideas and views, is a phenomenon that arises through the interplay of various cognitive processes, emotional experiences, and perceptual stimuli.

The process of self-development, also known as self-knowledge, starts from the moment of birth. During the early stages of development, the kid lacks the ability to comprehend their own existence and is unable to differentiate between the self and the external world. The first step in establishing one's identity is the recognition and differentiation of one's own name from those who have the same name.

During the first stages of development, children acquire self-awareness via familial interactions, then progressing towards self-discovery within their peer groups as they gradually detach from parental dependence. Interaction analysis is the examination of potential interactions among several persons, which is contingent upon their self-states that are self-determined and restricted in number.

Argument

The Initial Impact and Visual Presentation for Captivating the Interest of Children: The concept of first impression pertains to the first observation of a certain characteristic, which then shapes one's perception of other characteristics, occurring rapidly and upon immediate visual encounter. Despite providing just a limited snapshot of an individual based on a brief interaction, this approach yields a substantial proportion of data that may be used to make inferences about the person.

CURRENT SCIENCE

Hair is a significant aspect that effectively conveys an individual's appearance and lifestyle. The hairstyle of individuals may serve as a reflection of several characteristics such as age, emotions, economic standing, and maturity.

Attire Preference: Adhering to the practice of concealing one's limbs and torso. The attire individuals choose to wear serves as a means of communicating social signals. This provides details pertaining to the fabric composition, coloration, style, texture, model, as well as the individual's values, objectives, and personal preferences. The selection of attire conveys indications that articulate the individual's profession and socioeconomic standing.

Accessories refer to tools or items that are regarded as supplementary components of attire. Accessories serve the dual purpose of embellishing individuals' bodies and garments, while also providing valuable insights about their personal attributes and sartorial preferences.

The face has discernible characteristics during interpersonal interactions. In the context of interpersonal communication, the face assumes a significant function by capturing attention before to other bodily features. Communicators possess the ability to comprehend nonverbal cues and responses via the observation of facial expressions.

Eye behavior encompasses several aspects of visual perception and communication, including but not limited to eye movement and eye contact. The observation of eye activity is easily identifiable due to its direct visibility. Animation and motion are other significant attributes associated with the eyes.

Research Strategy

Social psychologists are primarily interested in studying the behavior of individuals within groups, as well as investigating the impact that groups have on its members. Social psychology is an empirical discipline that seeks to systematically investigate the cognitive processes individuals use when seeing and evaluating others, the influence that others have on their thoughts, emotions, and behaviors, as well as the dynamics of interpersonal relationships and interactions.

The social psychological approach is used not just by sociologists, but also by economists, political scientists, and other scholars in the social sciences. Researchers in the field of social

CURRENT SCIENCE

sciences endeavor to comprehend and elucidate overarching trends in societal conduct, including phenomena such as rates of murder, voting habits, and consumer expenditure.

The phenomenon may be attributed to several challenges, including economic hardships, class disparities, intergroup disputes, regional productivity limitations, governmental regulations, and technology advancements. The primary objective of social analysis is to elucidate the connections between overarching social factors and overarching patterns of social behavior.

The self-analysis level is often used by clinical psychologists and personality psychologists. Behavior is explicated by psychologists via the lens of an individual's distinct life trajectory and psychological attributes. This approach posits that personality characteristics and intentions influence an individual's engagement in certain activities and account for the differential reactions shown by two persons in response to the identical event.

Social psychologists have embraced an alternative level of analysis:

At the interpersonal level, social psychologists often direct their attention on an individual's present social context. The social context encompasses the presence of individuals within a given location, as well as their attitudes, actions, and interpersonal dynamics. To comprehend violent crimes, social psychologists place emphasis on the role of interpersonal interactions in augmenting hostility and eliciting sentiments of wrath.

Based on a social psychology perspective, it is posited that circumstances characterized by inhibition might elicit feelings of anger in individuals, thereby increasing their inclination towards engaging in aggressive behaviors. The phenomenon at hand is often referred to as the aggressiveness hypothesis.

All three methods, namely the societal, individual, and interpersonal, have significant value. They endeavor to ascertain solutions to several inquiries, including the underlying factors contributing to acts of violence, using an alternative approach.

The historical origins of social psychology may be traced back to the work of Sigmund Freud, who is often regarded as the progenitor of psychoanalytic theory. Freud's research focused on exploring the intricate psychological experiences of human beings. The author posits that human behavior is fundamentally driven by innate and powerful instincts and urges, such as sexuality and violence.

CURRENT SCIENCE

The individual posits that adult actions are shaped by unresolved psychological issues that may be traced back to childhood events within the familial context. Psychoanalytic theorists aim to comprehend the interplay between scientific and subconscious factors that directly influence human behavior.

Behaviorism has adopted a distinct approach towards the study of human behavior. Behaviorism, a psychological perspective pioneered by notable figures such as I. Pavlov, John B. Watson, and B.F. Skinner, places emphasis on the examination of observable behaviors shown by both humans and other animals.

Behaviorists do not prioritize subjective sensations and ideas due to their perception of these aspects as immaterial, difficult to quantify, hence lacking scientific validity.

The Gestalt approach to psychology was developed by prominent European psychologists, including Wolfgang Kohler, Kurt Koffka, Kurt Lewin, and others who relocated to the United States during the 1930s. Psychologists have directed their attention on the examination of individuals' cognitive processes in relation to their comprehension of things, events, and others. According to their perspective, individuals possess the ability to comprehend situations or occurrences as integrated entities including several discrete components.

Theories in Social Psychology

Motivational theories mostly focus on the intrinsic wants and motivations of individuals. Both everyday experiences and sociological studies provide valuable insights into the ways in which our perceptions, attitudes, and actions influence our needs.

The Freudian or psychoanalytic perspective on human drives places significant emphasis on several powerful and inherent urges, with a particular focus on those pertaining to sexuality and violence. In contrast, social psychologists direct their attention on a distinct realm of human wants and desires. Additionally, their attention is directed towards examining how the circumstances and social dynamics might give rise to various wants and reasons.

The study of learning theories is a fundamental aspect of educational research and practice. These theories provide a framework for understanding how individuals acquire knowledge. Based on the fundamental tenets of learning theories, an individual's present behavior may be

CURRENT SCIENCE

attributed to prior experiences. In various contexts, individuals acquire certain patterns of behavior that may develop into habitual tendencies over time, leading to their repetition upon subsequent re-engagement with the same context.

As an example, it is common practice for individuals to come to a halt when a traffic light transitions to the color red. As this response has been previously studied and documented. The phenomenon of social behavior analysis by individuals is often referred to as social learning theory. The process of learning may occur via three distinct mechanisms, one of which is known as associative or classical conditioning. Reinforcement, observational, or observational learning refers to a cognitive process in which individuals acquire knowledge, skills, or behaviors by seeing and imitating others, and may also be influenced by the consequences or reinforcements associated with such behaviors.

Cognitive theories claim that an individual's conduct is contingent upon their cognitive interpretation of the surrounding social context. Kurt Lewin used the principles of Gestalt psychology within the field of social psychology. The significance of the social environment as seen by the person was emphasized. The term "psychological field" is used to refer to the social environment in relation to the concept of the person. Behavior is subject to the impact of both intrinsic factors, including an individual's inherent abilities, personality traits, and genetic predispositions, as well as extrinsic factors, namely the social environment as it is subjectively seen by the individual.

A fundamental concept within the cognitive viewpoint pertains to individuals' inclination to instinctively classify and categorize various items.

Cognitive methods and learning techniques may be distinguished based on two essential aspects. Cognitive methods prioritize present perceptions above previous learning and emphasize the significance of an individual's view or interpretation of a given circumstance.

The study of decision theories encompasses a range of theoretical frameworks and models that aim to understand and explain the process of decision-making. These According to choose theories, people incur benefits and costs associated with certain behavior types. Upon careful evaluation of the observed actions, individuals demonstrate a rational and intelligent approach in determining the most optimal course of action. They exhibit a preference for colors that provide the lowest cost and highest returns. The expectancy value theory enhances the reward-cost perspective by including an evaluation of the likelihood of each alternative materializing.

CURRENT SCIENCE

This paper examines the ideas of interdependence, which include the analysis of how the conduct of individuals or groups is influenced by their interactions with one another. For instance, in the context of a father assisting his small kid with dressing, the father may demonstrate the process of buttoning a shirt and express affection via a loving embrace, perhaps fostering mutual interest between them. The phenomenon of mutual influence refers to the reciprocal impact that emotions, beliefs, and actions have on one another. Two individuals the concept of interdependence suggests that if an individual's benefits are contingent upon a certain factor, it is inappropriate to express anger against that factor, since it signifies a reliance on external circumstances for one's income.

The social and cultural aspects Social cultural theories propose that individuals possess diverse social backgrounds, which may significantly vary from one another. There is a growing worry among social psychologists about the impact of diverse subject backgrounds on individuals' cognitive processes, emotional experiences, and behavioral tendencies.

Psychologists have recognized the significance of culture in their efforts to comprehend variations. Beliefs that are commonly held among certain groups might be characterized as conventions and behavioral norms, including national, ethnic, and religious collectives. The process of culture socialization, which involves the transmission of cultural values and norms to the next generation, may be seen in many social organizations, including adolescent gangs and college fraternity groups. These groups use a method known as n1q song to impart cultural knowledge and socialize its members. The communal cultural viewpoint refers to the interpretation of conduct within a certain social or cultural context. The sociocultural approach places emphasis on the comparative analysis of diverse civilizations or social groupings.

One cannot overlook a significant aspect until a thorough examination is conducted on the cultural influences that our own culture may not see as the norm or the most suitable conduct.

Evolutionary social psychology is a field of study that utilizes the ideas of evolution and natural selection to gain insights into human behavior and social dynamics. Evolutionary social psychology incorporates concepts that were afterwards established by biologists and were proposed in the magazine *Beginnings*, in order to explain the phenomenon of social bloat seen in many species such as insects, birds, and other animals. Cultural methods place emphasis on the variation seen in human behavior throughout different regions of the globe, while home-based approaches focus on the shared human attributes that arise from the dispersed transmission of our ancestral history. Psychology encompasses several perspectives that have

CURRENT SCIENCE

significant centrality. It is noteworthy that numerous human inclinations and preferences may be attributed to the process of natural selection.

Participant Selection: Determining the Criteria for Research Subjects An essential first step is doing a comprehensive examination of the individuals (research population) whose findings one aims to extrapolate. In order to ensure the generalizability of the findings to the population of full-time women, it is advisable to include only full-time women in the study. Nevertheless, it is evident that their scope is limited to a subset of women who are employed full-time, rather than including the whole population.

Hence, a limited subset of women engaged in full-time employment, chosen to serve as representatives of the broader population, are eligible to partake as subjects in their study, a phenomenon often referred to as small-scale sampling. The representative sample was selected and represented by a group. One effective method for obtaining comfort is by the absence of any negative experiences with my elder son, as shown by his lack of interaction with you. The inquiry pertains to the concept of random selection, specifically in terms of equal probability. An illustrative case is sought to elucidate the rationale behind the participation of everyone within the biggest group in the act of riding.

The determination of the data gathering strategy to be used as the subsequent stage in research may be categorized into three fundamental alternatives.

Conclusion

Games have a crucial role in fostering the wholesome spiritual growth of persons. Engaging in play activities has been identified as a very effective approach to facilitate a child's learning process. Creative theater classes are founded on the concept of play, a notion that has gained recognition from both social theorists and educational scientists in recent times. Various qualities, including happiness, camaraderie, kindness, honesty, and tolerance, are seen in all contexts where the game is engaged in. The reason for the need of happiness in relation to current qualities is evident.

Many individuals get great pleasure from engaging in gaming activities. Traditional games are one of the categories of games that are essential for children's enjoyment of playing. Traditional games are a category of activities that serve as manifestations of the societal values, culture,

CURRENT SCIENCE

traditions, and customs within a certain community (Bozkurt and Sözer, 2018: 304). It is important that children engage in physical activities and participate in games. It is important for the person to possess a comprehensive understanding of the regulations governing the game. Additionally, they should formulate a strategic approach to maximize their chances of success. Furthermore, they should assume a feeling of accountability in representing their team. The ability to effectively allocate attentional resources is also crucial. Moreover, it is essential for the individual to get satisfaction and enjoyment from the act of playing. In the event of an error, the individual should be capable of recognizing their mistake and accepting the corresponding consequences in accordance with the established guidelines within the classroom setting. In order to instill values in children, it is essential to provide surroundings that facilitate experiential learning rather than relying just on didactic lectures. Additionally, it is crucial to afford children the chance to engage in play. Engaging in traditional games at home or in educational settings offers children an enjoyable experience that simultaneously facilitates their learning process. This is the process through which enduring knowledge acquisition occurs.

References

- Alkaya Yener Yeşim, (Pamukkale University Education Faculty Der. S/N: 29 January 2011-I) Analysis Of Storybooks in Terms of Some Basic Values”, Cumhuriyet International Journal of Education -Cije, 3(2), 44-69.
- Bursa Uludag University, Journal of The Faculty of Education Xx (2), 243-266.
- Children's Games Played by Children in Turkey in Past Years. Basar, Ha (2007).
- Cihan, N. (2014). Values Education in Schools and An Overview of Practice in Turkey. Turkish Studies
- Comert, S. (1976). Game And Ronts. Istanbul: Remzi Bookstore.
- Coruk Tuğba, Master Thesis Proposal (Cumhuriyet University Institute of Educational Sciences, 2013)
- Deniz, K. And Karagöl, E. (2018). “Secondary School Turkish Textbooks in Terms of Values Education”,

CURRENT SCIENCE

Dirican, R. And Dağlıoğlu, He (2014). “Illustrated Pictures Published For 3-6 Age Group Children”

Ekici Tülay, (Çankırı Karatekin University Journal of Social Sciences Institute 1(2010): 159-182)

Flood, R. (1974). Educational Game. Ankara: Ayyıldız Press, 2nd Edition.

Game And Magic. Istanbul: Yapıkredi Publications. And M. (2007).

Güneş Modiri Işıl, Eğt. Fac. Der. 23 (2), 2010, 505-516

Honor, Bg (2004). Children's Games in Turkey: Studies. Ankara: Ankara University Children's

International Periodical for The Languages, Literature and History of English or Turkish
Volume

Investigation Of Teaching the Value of Responsibility with Handkerchief Grab Game with
Vignette Technique. Turkish Studies, Volume 13/27, 299-325. Bozkurt, E. And Sözer, Ma
(2018).

Kahyaoglu, Yılmaz “Sociology of Education and Music” Art Magazine

Karaçay Bahri, “Music and Brain” Science and Technology July 2010,

Karaelmas Journal of Educational Sciences, Volume 6, Issue 2.

Koca Şehirban (Assoc.Prof. Dr.), “(Mersin University, Faculty of Education, Department of
Primary Education, Associate Professor of School, Usa)

Kolaç, E. (2010). “Values And Tolerance Education in Turkish Lessons with The Philosophy
of Hacı Bektaş Veli, Mevlana and Yunus” Turkish Culture and Hacı Bektaş Veli

Kudret, C. (1973). Middlegame. Ankara: Türkiye İş Bankası Publications.

Kuşcu Özden (Res.Assist.), Kayili Gökhan (Res.Assist.), Barişeri Nurtuğ (Assoc.Prof. Dr.)
(Selçuk University Vocational Education Faculty, Necmettin Erbakan University Ahmet
Keleşoğlu Education Faculty)

Öziskender Gülin, Güdek Bahar Turk.Vol. 8-3, Win. / 2013)

CURRENT SCIENCE

Özyürek Arzu, Aydoğan Yasemin “Examination of Preschool Teachers' Practices Regarding Leisure Activities” (Sakarya University Faculty of Education Journal, 22 (December 2011), Pp. 41-58.)

Sendurur Yılmaz, Akgül Bariş Dolunay “G.Ü. Gazi Education Faculty Journal Vol 22, No:1 (2002) 165-174

Sigirtmaç Ayperi (Dr.) Ç.Ü. Faculty of Education Department of Primary Education

Sümbüllü, Yz (2016). The Importance of Traditional Children's Games in Values Education. *Etu*,

Şen Yavuz, “The Importance of Music in The Development of The Child in Preschool Period”

Tuesday Güneş, Akkol Mümtaz Levent, Oğuz Vuslat “The Problems Preschool Teachers Experience in Music Events”

Yıldırım, A. And Şimşek, H. (2000). *Qualitative Research Methods in Social Sciences*, Ankara: Seçkin Publications.

Yildiz Evren (Research Assistant), Şen Yavuz (Research Assistant) “The Importance of Music and Piano Education at Young Ages”

Yildiz, Ahmet (“Strong Memory” 14th Edition December/2014)